

Responsible Futures Skills

Lab 6-7 May 2026

Research for Responsible Futures

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Responsible Futures Skills Lab 6-7 May 2026

Day 2: Research For Responsible Futures

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Day 2: Research For Responsible Futures – Roundtable Discussion Moderators

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Executive Summary

Day 2 of the **Responsible Futures Skills Lab** shifted the focus from teaching to **Research for Responsible Futures**. Building on Day 1's discussion of pedagogy, interdisciplinarity, assessment, and responsible futures education, the second day examined how cross-disciplinary research can be designed, negotiated, published, and sustained within the institutional realities of academia.

The day was structured around a central question: **How do we make cross-disciplinary research work — academically, institutionally, and beyond our own field?**

The programme brought together business school scholars, climate scientists, modellers, operations scholars, journal editors, and participants from different disciplines and institutions. Sessions included an opening research framing, a cross-disciplinary panel on what different fields need from one another, a research-in-action spotlight on the **Net Zero Research Village (NeRV)** project, an editor dialogue on publishing cross-disciplinary research, facilitated roundtables, and a collective synthesis.

A recurring insight was that cross-disciplinary research is not simply disciplinary research with additional collaborators attached. It requires a different design logic from the outset. Researchers need to clarify assumptions, language, methods, outputs, authorship, publication strategies, impact pathways, and career risks early in the process.

The day also surfaced a structural tension. Universities, funders, and policy communities increasingly call for interdisciplinary, challenge-led, societally relevant research. Yet academic careers, journal hierarchies, REF pressures, promotion criteria, and disciplinary evaluation systems still often reward work that is more easily recognisable within established fields. This creates particular risks for early-career researchers and for colleagues whose work sits between disciplinary communities.

Cross-disciplinary research does not happen just by putting people from different fields in the same room. It takes time to build a shared language, understand different standards of evidence, and work out what counts as contribution, rigour, and impact. That work is often invisible, but it is central to whether collaboration succeeds.

Overall, Day 2 generated seven key insights:

- **Cross-disciplinary research must begin with the problem, not the team.**
- **Translation across disciplines is intellectual work and must be designed into projects.**
- **Disciplinary assumptions need to be surfaced early.**
- **Cross-disciplinary work can become extractive unless credit, ownership, and outputs are negotiated explicitly.**
- **Publication strategy must be considered from the beginning, not after the research is complete.**
- **Policy, practice, and stakeholder relevance can strengthen cross-disciplinary research, but only when integrated into the design.**
- **Institutions need to create research environments where interdisciplinary work is not a career risk, but a recognised part of academic work.**

Noemi Sinkovics' closing remarks underlined that, while some of these issues may be familiar to those already working in this area, they remain important to revisit. New colleagues continue to enter these conversations, and shared understanding develops gradually through repeated exchange. In this sense, the value of the discussion was not only in generating resonance, but in helping to make participants more attuned to the challenges, legitimise the work involved, and mobilise further action.

Introduction: Why a Responsible Futures Skills Lab?

The **Responsible Futures Skills Lab** was designed as a reflective, practice-oriented forum for exploring how responsible and sustainable futures can be meaningfully integrated into teaching design and research practice. Day 1 focused on pedagogical approaches for responsible futures education. Day 2 moved from teaching to research.

This shift from teaching to research was deliberate. The same challenges that shape responsible futures education also shape responsible futures research: **complexity, uncertainty, competing forms of evidence, different disciplinary languages, institutional constraints, and questions of impact.**

Responsible futures research often addresses problems that do not sit neatly within one field: climate transition, AI governance, migration, health inequalities, regional development, sustainable consumption, financial inclusion, public trust, organisational resilience, and industrial transformation.

These problems involve technologies, markets, institutions, communities, policies, behaviours, cultures, and histories simultaneously. However, the academic system remains largely organised around disciplines, departments, journal rankings, disciplinary panels, and established epistemic communities. The result is a persistent tension between the problems researchers need to address and the structures through which research is evaluated.

Day 2 therefore asked: **How can cross-disciplinary research be designed so that it is intellectually serious, methodologically credible, meaningful to stakeholders, publishable for different collaborators, and sustainable for academic careers?**

Institutional research pressures and cross-disciplinary design

Abigail Marks, Associate Dean Research at Newcastle University Business School, framed the day by reflecting on the research environment in which business school academics currently operate. She reminded participants that almost every major societal challenge is cross-disciplinary by nature, yet academic systems still reward disciplinary clarity, methodological familiarity, and publication within recognised epistemic communities.

She identified several overlapping pressures. First, publication and research quality remain central to academic careers. Hiring, promotion, institutional reputation, and individual progression are still closely tied to publication in highly ranked journals. **In many business schools, journal lists continue to shape research behaviour.**

Second, **external funding** increasingly calls for interdisciplinarity, stakeholder engagement, challenged research, and demonstrable societal relevance. Yet **proposals are often assessed through disciplinary panels, disciplinary assumptions, and discipline-specific standards of evidence.**

Third, Research Excellence Framework (REF) pressures add another layer of complexity. While REF rewards originality, significance, rigour, and wider contribution, **institutions also manage risk. Cross-disciplinary work can be perceived as harder to place, harder to evaluate, and less predictable in publication trajectory.**

This creates mixed signals for researchers. They are encouraged to be interdisciplinary, engage stakeholders, collaborate across sectors, address grand challenges, and pursue societal relevance. At the same time, they are encouraged to publish in elite disciplinary journals, maintain methodological purity, sustain a coherent disciplinary identity, and produce outputs that remain legible to established evaluation systems.

Abigail's core message was that **cross-disciplinary research** is not simply disciplinary research with collaborators added. It **requires a different design logic from the beginning.**

Topic overlap is not enough. Two researchers may both

work on sustainability, AI, inequality, or health, but operate with fundamentally different assumptions about evidence, explanation, contribution, and rigour. One field may prioritise causal identification; another may prioritise meaning and interpretation. One may value abstraction and generalisability; another may value contextual depth. One may seek prediction; another may seek critique or reflexivity. These differences are not superficial. They are epistemological. If they are not surfaced early, collaborations can become fragile.

Abigail also warned against **extractive forms of interdisciplinarity**. In some projects, one discipline supplies the theory, another supplies data, another contributes technical expertise, and another provides stakeholder access or impact. **Genuine cross-disciplinary work requires intellectual co-production: collaborators jointly shaping the problem framing, research questions, methods, interpretation, and outputs.**

Translation was identified as one of the **most underestimated elements of interdisciplinary work**. Explaining concepts, assumptions, and methods across disciplinary boundaries is not administrative overhead. It is intellectual work. Often, this is where some of the most valuable thinking happens.

Abigail suggested five principles for careful cross-disciplinary design:

- **begin with the problem, not the discipline**
- **make epistemological assumptions explicit early**
- **design for multiple forms of output from the beginning**
- **recognise translation as intellectual work**
- **think institutionally as well as intellectually**

She also made a crucial point about responsible research. Cross-disciplinary work is not automatically more ethical, more impactful, or more innovative. It can produce superficial synthesis if it is treated as branding rather than as serious intellectual integration. **The goal is not interdisciplinarity for its own sake. The goal is a better understanding of genuinely complex problems.**

Cross-disciplinary opening panel: What do we need from other disciplines?

The opening panel brought together **Laura Marsiliani, Ursula Ott, Roy Sanderson, Hayley Fowler, and Chris Hicks**, chaired by **Noemi Sinkovics**. The session began from the premise that cross-disciplinary research should not be justified only in abstract terms. The question was practical: where does one discipline stop being enough? The panel brought together perspectives from economics, international business, modelling, climate science, and operations management. The discussion surfaced both the necessity and the difficulty of cross-disciplinary research.

Economics, place, and human behaviour

Laura Marsiliani argued that economics alone cannot solve the problems it most needs to address. Technology and innovation are essential inputs into the net-zero transition, but they cannot be fully analysed without engineering, material science, computing, sociology, psychology, and place-based understanding. A key theme in her contribution was **the need to capture the realities of place-based communities**. The net-zero transition will affect communities differently. **Models that ignore geography, culture, local political economy, and social context risk producing poor policy**. Economic models of human behaviour are still often built around assumptions of rational self-interest, which have many times been proven incomplete when trying to understand how people and communities respond to major transitions. Laura's contribution showed why **cross-disciplinary research** is not just a matter of adding perspectives. **It is necessary because the problem itself exceeds the explanatory capacity of one field.**

Assumptions, disciplinary humility, and international business

Ursula Ott emphasised that basic assumptions matter enormously. Every discipline has foundational assumptions about how the world works, but these assumptions are often invisible to those working

within the discipline. **Interdisciplinary research** is therefore partly a process of making assumptions visible to people who do not share them. It **requires researchers to recognise that their own concepts, methods, and standards may not be self-evident or universally persuasive**. Ursula **cautioned against disciplinary purism**. Excessive commitment to **disciplinary orthodoxy can become an obstacle to both good research and good policy**. She illustrated this with the example of a mining project in Nigeria, where what initially appeared to be an engineering problem also involved health, labour rights, community wellbeing, and political economy. Each disciplinary lens revealed a different layer of the problem.

Modelling, technology, and human behaviour

Roy Sanderson offered a powerful case study of the gap between technological solutions and human reality. In a precision agriculture project, farms were equipped with cameras, sensors, and AI systems to regulate nitrate application automatically. The technology worked and the data was good. Yet nitrate levels did not fall because farmers overrode the system. They did not trust it. The lesson was: **technically correct solutions can fail without an understanding of human behaviour**. Roy's example was not a general call for social science consultation after the fact. It was a call for genuine collaboration from the outset. If the behavioural, social, and institutional dimensions of technology adoption are not designed into the project, the project may fail even when the technology itself performs well. He also emphasised **the importance of open data quality**. In projects that cross jurisdictions, such as work involving the Tweed across the Scottish-English border, different data collection standards can make integration slow and costly. **What may appear to be a technical data problem can become a major obstacle to research design and impact.**

Cross-disciplinary opening panel: What do we need from other disciplines?

Climate evidence, adaptation, and community response

Hayley Fowler expanded the discussion of behavioural complexity through the example of flooding. Even when flood risk is communicated clearly and accurately, communities may not respond in ways that reduce vulnerability. This example highlighted a wider issue in climate adaptation: physical science can identify risk, but reducing vulnerability requires understanding behaviour, institutions, communication, trust, place, and action. The behavioural and social dimensions of climate adaptation are therefore not secondary. They need to be designed in from the start. Hayley also emphasised that stakeholder engagement must be embedded early. **Transdisciplinary research that includes practitioners is more complex, but it can produce more durable impact.**

Sustainability, operations, and the DNA of the project

Christian Hicks introduced work addressing sustainability within the military defence sector, an area where sustainability is increasingly urgent but rarely discussed in business school research. His contribution underscored the importance of understanding the practical contexts in which sustainability challenges are situated. Christian offered a key design principle for interdisciplinary research: **Think about the contribution you are looking to achieve. Understand the DNA of the project. Scope is not enough.** This means that collaboration should not begin merely by defining a topic. It should begin by clarifying what kind of contribution the project seeks to make, who needs to use the findings, what evidence is required, and what outputs will be meaningful.

Why the same problem looks different across fields

One of the most important discussions in the opening panel concerned why the same problem

appears different from different disciplinary perspectives.

Laura Marsiliani noted that every problem has multiple dimensions: financial, cultural, political, technical, behavioural, institutional. Each discipline has tools that illuminate some of these dimensions and leave others in the shadow. **Ursula Ott's** mining example demonstrated the same point. What appears as an engineering problem from one perspective may become a health problem, labour problem, community problem, governance problem, or international business problem from another.

The panel showed that **interdisciplinary collaboration gets difficult not because researchers disagree that a problem matters, but because they are often not asking the same question.** They may be working at different levels of analysis, using different timescales, valuing different kinds of evidence, or imagining different audiences.

This has direct implications for research design.

Before a project begins, collaborators need to ask:

- **What problem are we each trying to solve?**
- **What does each discipline see clearly?**
- **What does each discipline tend to miss?**
- **What counts as good evidence?**
- **What does contribution mean?**
- **What outputs matter?**
- **Who are the intended audiences?**
- **What kinds of impact are plausible?**

Without these conversations, cross-disciplinary projects risk becoming collections of parallel workstreams rather than integrated research.

Where collaboration gets stuck

The opening panel and later roundtables identified several recurring points where cross-disciplinary research becomes difficult.

Data, standards, and integration

Roy Sanderson highlighted the importance of open data quality and the difficulty of integrating data collected under different standards. This is not merely a technical issue. Data standards reflect institutional histories, regulatory frameworks, professional norms, and assumptions about what matters.

Stakeholder engagement

Hayley Fowler emphasised that stakeholder engagement must be designed from the start. If practitioners, communities, policymakers, or users are brought in too late, they may be asked only to validate a project that was not designed around their realities.

Project instability

Christian Hicks noted practical failure points that affect many projects: people changing jobs, political environments changing, funding priorities shifting, or established methods being challenged while the project is already underway. Cross-disciplinary research often depends on fragile alignments, and these can be disrupted by events outside the research team's control.

Professional isolation

Ursula Ott observed that interdisciplinary researchers may not always be understood or valued within their own disciplines. This can be professionally costly. Researchers working between fields may struggle to find mentors, reviewers, journals, or promotion narratives that fully recognise their contribution.

Journal and career risks

The panel also discussed the challenge of joint publications across fields. **Different collaborators may need different kinds of outputs. Some may need top-ranked disciplinary journal articles; others may need policy impact, technical outputs, practitioner reports, or stakeholder engagement.** If these needs are not discussed early, collaboration can become frustrating or unfair. **Roy Sanderson** captured the issue succinctly: **it is not just about publishing; it is about impact and policy change.** In some projects, the most meaningful outcome may be behavioural change among farmers, changes in water management, or contributions to fishing quota policy. Such outcomes may not have an obvious journal home, but they may be central to the value of the research.

Research in Action Spotlight: The NeRV project

The **Research in Action Spotlight** focused on the NeRV Project, with **Joanne Swaffield** presenting an interdisciplinary case of research design in practice.

The project examines the adoption and acceptability of energy-related retrofit technologies in the home, using Futures Close, a purpose-built test site of nine properties in Winlaton, Gateshead. The site reflects different eras of UK housing stock and provides a concrete setting for exploring how energy-efficient technologies perform across different building types, and how members of the public respond to them in practice.

A central insight from the project is that the adoption of sustainable home technologies is not only a technical question. It is also social, behavioural, cultural, and practical. Technologies may appear promising in terms of performance, efficiency, or value for money, but their success depends on whether people understand them, trust them, can afford them, and see them as compatible with everyday home life.

The project combines technical testing with social research, including interviews, walking groups, and focus groups with participants from across the North East, including potentially vulnerable participants. This created opportunities for richer insight but also exposed the practical challenges of collaborative research: logistics, sequencing, time pressure, recruitment, competing priorities around results and outputs, and differences in definitions, sampling, and working style.

For management scholarship, the case shows why responsible futures research needs to take adoption, implementation, and impact seriously. Businesses, policymakers, and technology providers cannot assume that households will accept retrofit solutions simply because they support net-zero goals. Design, communication, deployment, and support all matter.

The NeRV spotlight gave participants a concrete example of the issues discussed throughout Day 2: **the need for early design conversations, methodological negotiation, shared language, and careful thinking about how research can generate both academic insight and practical impact.**

For more information, visit <https://ebusiness.ncl.ac.uk/projects/customer-energy-village/>

The ebusiness@newcastle research team is led by **Prof. Savvas Papagiannidis**, Newcastle University Business School.

Editor Dialogue: Publishing Cross-Disciplinary Research

The afternoon editor dialogue was moderated by **Alex Hope** and brought together editors and editorial representatives from a range of journals: **Tazeeb Rajwani** (*Academy of Management Perspectives* and *Multinational Business Review*), **Antje Fiedler** (*Small Business Economics* and *Journal of Small Business Management*), **Rudolf Sinkovics** (*Critical Perspectives on International Business*), **Noemi Sinkovics** (*European Management Journal*), **Cristina Neesham** (*Business and Society* and *Philosophy of Management*), **Irene Chu** (*Business Strategy and the Environment*), **Victoria Pagan** (*Culture and Organisation*), **Rob van Tulder** (*Journal of International Business Policy*), and **Matthew Allen** (*International Studies of Management & Organization*).

The purpose of the session was not to promote individual journals, but to understand how journals respond to cross-disciplinary work, where barriers arise, and what authors can learn from editorial perspectives. A central question guided the discussion: **Does cross-disciplinary work get a fair chance?**

The answer was nuanced. Some journals are actively creating space for cross-disciplinary, policy-facing, practice-facing, or impact-oriented research. However, cross-disciplinary papers can still struggle when they do not fit clearly into established theoretical, methodological, or contribution categories.

Editorial decisions are made by people, not journals

Noemi Sinkovics emphasised that the fate of a cross-disciplinary paper may depend on whose desk it lands on. Editorial decisions are made by people, not by journals in the abstract. The ecosystem of a journal — including its editorial board, reviewer pool, editor training, and editorial culture — shapes what is possible. For cross-disciplinary work, communication between editors and reviewers is critical. Such papers need reviewers who can evaluate them fairly, not

reviewers who judge them only from one disciplinary standpoint. Editors therefore play an important role in framing the review process and helping reviewers understand the intended contribution.

Matching papers with the right editorial expertise

Victoria Pagan discussed the importance of authors clearly setting out in their writing what it is they are aiming to achieve. The aim and purpose of the paper should be evident from the outset and carried throughout the piece. A lack of such clarity may lead to premature rejection. She explained that Culture and Organisation works to match papers with Associate Editors from a large and diverse editorial board who have relevant expertise. She also noted the value of “reject and resubmit” decisions with developmental feedback for cross-disciplinary work that has promise but needs significant revision. This can give authors a route to develop the paper rather than receiving a simple negative decision.

Policy-facing international business research

Rob van Tulder explained that the Journal of International Business Policy was founded to create space for work that bridges international business theory and policy practice — work that may struggle in more traditional international business journals. He emphasised the importance of engaged scholarship that holds rigour and relevance together. The challenge is not to choose between robust research and policy relevance, but to produce work that is both theoretically meaningful and practically useful.

Article formats and editorial infrastructure

Cristina Neesham argued that editorial infrastructure needs to improve. The challenges facing cross-disciplinary research are structural, not only individual. She highlighted the importance of using different article formats, including essays,

Editor Dialogue: Publishing Cross-Disciplinary Research

heterodox approaches, experimental work, and commentaries. Not every interdisciplinary contribution fits the standard empirical paper format. Collaborative authorship across disciplines can also be an important signal to editors that genuine interdisciplinary work is taking place.

Theory, contribution, and educational research

Irene Chu stressed that empirical findings alone are not enough if a journal expects theoretical contribution. **Noemi Sinkovics** added that what counts as theory is broader than many authors and reviewers assume.

Joining an existing conversation

Tazeeb Rajwani reminded participants that journals have boundaries, and these boundaries are not arbitrary. Submitting to a journal means joining a conversation that has often been ongoing for years. Authors need to bridge to that conversation rather than simply presenting their own research question. This is especially important when bridging distant disciplines. Reviewers from each discipline will scrutinise whether the paper has done justice to their field. The bridge must therefore be carefully constructed. He also noted that Academy of Management Perspectives explicitly values practical management implications and includes practitioners in its editorial ecosystem. This creates opportunities for work that can inform real management decisions.

The system is stretched — but opportunities exist

Rudolf Sinkovics offered a more critical view, arguing that the academic system is stretched in the sense that incentives for authors, editors, and reviewers are often misaligned with producing the best or most impactful research. However, he also emphasised the importance of seeking opportunities within the system. Strategic positioning, choosing the right journal, building relationships with editors and signalling fit clearly all matter. In response to a question about terminology, he noted that journals higher in the academic pecking

order are frequently more parochial and risk-averse, which paradoxically may lead to suppression of topic innovation.

Peer review as a system to improve, not abandon

Antje Fiedler provided a counterpoint, arguing that while the system is not perfect, it has produced an enormous body of reliable knowledge. The goal should be to improve peer review, not abandon it. This perspective helped balance critique of the system with recognition of the value that scholarly review can provide.

Emerging editorial space for interdisciplinary research

The editor dialogue closed with a recognition that editorial infrastructure is slowly catching up. Funding bodies, new journals, alternative article formats, and evolving editorial cultures are creating more space for cross-disciplinary work. However, as emphasised by **Matthew Allen**, authors can make this easier by being explicit about which disciplinary conversations they are bridging, why the bridge matters, and what kind of contribution they are making.

Two closing points were especially important.

First, there are different types of theory. Authors should not assume that theoretical contribution means only one thing. Grounded theory, conceptual frameworks, policy models, practice-based frameworks, and applied theory can all be legitimate if used carefully.

Second, the distinction between academic theory and practical frameworks is less absolute than it sometimes appears. Policy documents and applied frameworks often contain theoretical models, even if they are not labelled as such. Cross-disciplinary authors need to learn how to make those contributions visible to academic audiences.

Insights from the Facilitated Roundtables

What helps cross-disciplinary research work?

Several positive conditions were identified across the tables.

Trust and psychological safety were central.

Effective teams rely on interpersonal trust, often built through previous interactions. Cross-disciplinary work also requires humility and vulnerability.

Researchers need to be willing to listen, question their own assumptions, and sometimes give up long-held beliefs in order to co-create something new.

Mutual dependence is also important. Cross-disciplinary collaboration works best when researchers genuinely need one another. If one discipline can complete the project alone, others risk becoming decorative or extractive additions.

Complementarity of expertise helps teams work productively. Researchers need enough knowledge of other disciplines to make sense of their contributions, while also recognising that they cannot master everything.

Champions and boundary spanners are important structural support. Cross-disciplinary projects benefit from individuals who advocate for the work, connect people across institutional boundaries, and help navigate different reward systems.

Funding applications can also help structure interdisciplinary work. The act of writing a joint bid forces collaborators to clarify contributions, methods, and expected outputs.

Research centres and institutional homes can make cross-disciplinary work more viable. Centres that span disciplines, such as sustainable finance or technology innovation centres, can provide spaces where interdisciplinary work is normalised.

Knowledge Transfer Partnerships are useful mechanisms because they create structured university-industry collaboration with built-in

commercialisation pathways and grant funding.

Where does cross-disciplinary research get stuck?

The roundtables identified several recurring failure points. One major issue is the **difficulty of building relationships**. Common ground is hard to create through formal project meetings alone, and it is especially difficult when interactions take place only through digital platforms. Informal socialisation — meeting for coffee, talking across boundaries, developing trust — remains important.

Another issue is **disciplinary dogmatism**.

Researchers may remain attached to their own theories, methods, ontologies, and publication norms. This can make it difficult to think beyond disciplinary boundaries. Communication often stalls early. Teams may struggle to agree on the origin of the research question, the unit of analysis, data collection methods, publication strategy, or the meaning of key terms.

Different disciplines may value different outputs.

Books, journal articles, conference papers, policy reports, technical outputs, and commercialisation activities carry different levels of prestige across fields. Journal rankings vary by discipline and national context. This creates difficulty when collaborators need different outputs for career progression.

There are also **institutional constraints**: REF rules, promotion criteria, funding targets, departmental objectives, siloed conferences, and limited mentoring for interdisciplinary work.

Power asymmetries can also undermine collaboration. In some interdisciplinary projects, engineering, medicine, or STEM fields may dominate, while social science and business research are cast in supporting roles. This can undervalue qualitative research, even when qualitative insight is crucial to understanding adoption, implementation, or impact.

Insights from the Facilitated Roundtables

Practical disruptions also matter. Funding shortfalls, government priority changes, researcher mobility, and shifting team composition can all derail projects.

What should be clarified early?

The roundtables strongly emphasised the need for early clarification.

Teams should discuss:

- **the shared research question**
- **why the project is being undertaken**
- **what each participant wants from the project**
- **career interests and risks**
- **shared language and definitions**
- **research design and methodology**
- **data ownership**
- **authorship and author order**
- **publication strategy**
- **target journals and alternative outputs**
- **use of AI**
- **project management responsibilities**
- **conflict resolution**
- **cultural differences between disciplines**
- **stakeholder engagement**
- **supervision credit**
- **and expectations about timelines and deliverables**

Authorship was repeatedly identified as something that should be discussed at the beginning, not the end. This includes author order, principles for deciding authorship, and how different types of contribution will be recognised.

AI use emerged as an important new issue. It cannot be assumed that co-authors use or do not use AI in the same way. Teams need to clarify AI use because one person's use of AI may create ethical, copyright, or journal compliance risks for the whole author team.

The roundtables also emphasised that collaborators should **articulate the value of the project for each participant. Value may mean publication, impact, learning, network development, policy engagement, career progression, or commercialisation.** These differences are legitimate, but they need to be surfaced.

Opportunities for academic training

Several discussions pointed to a deeper issue in academic training. **Doctoral and early-career researchers are often trained to find solitary solutions and to become experts within disciplinary silos. They may not be trained in the humility, socialisation, negotiation, and translation required for interdisciplinary work.** This creates a **socialisation deficit.**

If future researchers are expected to work across disciplines, they need opportunities to develop those skills. Supervisors also play a crucial role in supporting PGRs to understand interdisciplinary collaboration, career risks, authorship norms, and the value of different forms of output.

The roundtables raised the need for training in:

- **interdisciplinary communication**
- **project management**
- **stakeholder engagement**
- **authorship and credit negotiation**
- **epistemological translation**
- **responsible AI use**
- **collaborative writing**
- **policy and impact pathways, and**
- **working across international as well as disciplinary contexts.**

Collective Synthesis

The collective synthesis, moderated by **Noemi Sinkovics**, drew together insights from the opening panel, NeRV spotlight, editor dialogue, and roundtables. Several design principles emerged.

Design for translation

The hardest work in interdisciplinary research is often translation. This includes **translation between concepts, methods, evidence standards, publication expectations, stakeholder needs, policy languages, and disciplinary assumptions**. Translation needs to be budgeted, planned, and valued. It should not be treated as a side task.

Start with the contribution, not the team

A common failure mode is assembling a team first and only later trying to find a research question that fits. A stronger approach is to start with the problem and contribution: What do we want to know? Why does it matter? Who is best placed to help us find out? This does not mean excluding serendipity or exploratory collaboration. It means that cross-disciplinary projects need a conceptual centre of gravity.

Build policy hooks early

Policy relevance should not be added as an afterthought. A clear policy hook can help protect interdisciplinary research from being dismissed as unfocused. It can also help identify audiences, outputs, stakeholders, and impact pathways from the beginning.

Be explicit about career risk

Interdisciplinary research is professionally risky. It can fall between journals, disciplines, REF units, promotion narratives, and reviewer expectations. This risk should be acknowledged rather than hidden. **Projects should be designed to generate disciplinary publications alongside interdisciplinary outputs where necessary.**

Clarify what “interdisciplinary” means

Participants noted the importance of distinguishing between multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary work. These terms are often used loosely. Teams should clarify what they mean in their specific project context. Are disciplines working in parallel? Are they integrating methods and theories? Are practitioners and non-academic actors involved in co-production? The answer matters for project design.

Recognise the role of project management

Project management skills are essential and undervalued in academia. Small funding and tight timeframes can sometimes help because they force alignment on deliverables. However, **effective interdisciplinary work also needs someone to manage communication, expectations, timelines, conflict, and outputs.**

Build research environments, not just projects

The final synthesis emphasised that cross-disciplinary research is not only an individual responsibility. Institutions need to build environments that support it. This includes connectors, boundary spanners, small seed funding, recognition in workload, support for interdisciplinary PGR training, spaces for relationship-building, and promotion systems that value collaboration and impact.

Practical Implications

For researchers

Researchers planning cross-disciplinary work are advised to begin by clarifying the problem, contribution, and intended audiences. They need to discuss assumptions, terminology, methods, outputs, authorship, AI use, publication plans, and impact pathways early. A useful starting set of questions is: What problem are we trying to understand or change? Why does this problem require more than one discipline? What does each discipline contribute? What does each discipline risk misunderstanding? What outputs does each collaborator need? What will count as success?

For research leaders

Research leaders need to recognise the time, uncertainty, and translation work involved in interdisciplinary collaboration. Support can include seed funding, facilitation, mentoring, project management support, workload recognition, and help with publication and impact strategy. Research leaders also need to pay attention to career risk. Early-career researchers may need protection and guidance to ensure that cross-disciplinary work produces outputs that are recognised within promotion and evaluation systems.

For doctoral training and supervision

PGRs need preparation for collaborative and interdisciplinary research. This includes training in communication, epistemological awareness, project management, authorship norms, responsible AI use, and impact pathways. PGRs may need help to understand both the opportunities and risks of interdisciplinary work. Supervisors need to model the humility and intellectual generosity required for such work to succeed.

For journals and editors

Editors can support cross-disciplinary research by improving reviewer matching, using developmental editorial practices, recognising alternative article formats, and helping reviewers understand the intended contribution of papers that bridge fields.

Authors can help editors by being explicit about the journal conversation they are joining, the disciplines they are bridging, the type of theory they are using, and the audience they seek to reach.

For funders and policy partners

Calls for interdisciplinary work need to be matched by review processes that can evaluate such work fairly. Policy partners can help by engaging early in project design, not only at dissemination stage. This makes it more likely that research questions, outputs, and impact pathways are aligned with real decision-making needs.

For business schools

To support interdisciplinary work, business schools need to align research strategy, workload, promotion, funding support, and impact infrastructure. Responsible futures research should not depend only on individual goodwill. Collaboration norms need to be codified and rewarded. Simultaneously, researchers should have the freedom to choose if and when they wish to embark on a cross-disciplinary journey.

For academies, professional associations, and global learning communities

They can create spaces where researchers from different disciplines, institutions, and career stages can meet. They can support the infrastructure around cross-disciplinary projects. This can include the facilitation of a shared language, trusted networks, examples of good practice, mentoring for early-career researchers, and forums where funders, journals, policymakers, practitioners, and researchers can speak to one another. They can also help shift norms by recognising cross-disciplinary and impact-oriented research as serious scholarly work, not as an add-on to disciplinary research.

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Resources

Journals represented in the Editor Dialogue

- Academy of Management Perspectives <https://www.aom.org/publications/journals/perspectives/>
- Multinational Business Review <https://www.emerald.com/mbr>
- Small Business Economics <https://link.springer.com/journal/11187>
- Journal of Small Business Management <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/ujbm20>
- Culture and Organisation <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/gsco20>
- European Management Journal <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/european-management-journal>
- Critical Perspectives on International Business <https://www.emerald.com/cpoib>
- Journal of International Business Policy <https://link.springer.com/journal/42214>
- Business and Society <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/bas>
- Business Strategy and the Environment <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10990836>
- Philosophy of Management <https://link.springer.com/journal/40926>
- International Studies of Management & Organization <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/mimo20>

Useful Resources

- Centre for Climate and Environmental Resilience <https://www.ncl.ac.uk/environmental-climate-resilience/>
- Academy of International Business UK&I Chapter <https://www.aib-uki.org/>
- British Academy of Management <https://www.bam.ac.uk>
- The Principles for Responsible Management Education (PRME) <https://www.unprme.org/>
- PRME UK&I Chapter <https://www.unprme.org.uk>

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